

Improving Proverb Search and Retrieval with a Generic Multi-dimensional Ontology

Zhitomirsky-Geffet, Maayan

Department of Information Science, Bar-Ilan University

Ramat-Gan, 5290002 Israel, Telephone: 972-3-5318351, Fax: 972-3-7384027

Maayan.Zhitomirsky-Geffet@biu.ac.il

Prebor, Gila

Department of Information Science, Bar-Ilan University

Ramat-Gan, 5290002 Israel, Telephone: 972-3-5318351, Fax: 972-3-7384027

Gila.Prebor@biu.ac.il

Bloch, Orna

Department of Information Science, Bar-Ilan University

Ramat-Gan, 5290002 Israel, Telephone: 972-3-5318351, Fax: 972-3-7384027

Ornab@digi-docu.com

Abstract

The goal of this research is to develop a generic ontological model for proverbs that unifies potential classification criteria and various characteristics of proverbs to enable their effective retrieval and large-scale analysis. Since proverbs can be described and indexed by multiple characteristics and criteria, we built a multi-dimensional ontology suitable for proverb classification. To evaluate the effectiveness of the constructed ontology for improving search and retrieval of proverbs, a large-scale user experiment was arranged with 70 users, who were asked to search a proverb repository using ontology-based and free-text search interfaces. The comparative analysis of the results shows that the use of this ontology helped to substantially improve the search recall, precision, user satisfaction, efficiency and to minimize user effort during the search process. A practical contribution of this work is an automated web-based proverb search and retrieval system which incorporates the proposed ontological scheme and an initial corpus of ontology-based annotated proverbs.

Introduction

Proverbs are a fascinating folklore genre which constitutes an important part of a nation's cultural heritage and reflects its collective wisdom. "The wisdom of nations lies in their proverbs... collect and learn them, they are notable measures of directions for human life..." (William Penn).

The study of proverbs has long been a subject of research by scholars from different disciplines, such as: folklorists, philologists, logicians, psychologists and anthropologists. Consequently, various research motivations and methods have produced diverse approaches towards organization and classification of proverbs into convenient indices for further search and retrieval. These approaches mostly differ in what should be considered key proverbial characteristic upon which an index or classification scheme should be devised, for example: text, logical or syntactic structure, context of usage, literary source, time and country of origin, or semantic field (Hasan-Rokem & Kats, 2009).

To resolve the above disagreements we propose to construct an ontology for proverbs. Ontologies have been proposed and widely employed in the past decade, as formal domain vocabularies specifying content-specific agreements for a variety of knowledge-sharing activities (Gruber, 1995). An ontology is a semantic scheme which comprises the main classes (concepts) of a given domain of knowledge, their properties, inter-relationships and instances (Noy & McGuinness, 2001). The basic ontological relationship types are IS-A (hyponymy) and instance-of (a concrete type-of) which constitute the basis of the concept hierarchy, but other thesauri-like (e.g. "part-of", "used-for") or content-driven relationships (e.g. "located-at", "produced-by") are allowed as well. A pair of concepts (or instances), *C1* and *C2*, and the relationship type, *R*, binding them semantically, constitute a triple of the form: (*C1 R C2*) representing an ontological relation and a fact on the domain of knowledge. For instance, (lion *IS-A* animal), (fire *causes* smoke), (Rome *instance-of* city). Further, some logical inference rules might be applied in order to create new relations (facts on the domain) that can be derived from the semantics of the existing relations in the ontology. Thus, the defined logical and semantic structure of ontologies makes them superior in applications, such as information retrieval, compared to thematic taxonomies based on unstructured heterogeneous associations between themes. For example, for a user query: "human personality traits", a search engine enhanced with the domain ontology will retrieve relevant documents even if they do not contain the exact query terms, but rather their related hyponymy concepts in the ontology, such as, "kindness", "jealousy", "diligence" and other specific traits.

One of the major challenges in proverb retrieval is that most proverbs are idiomatic and metaphoric, i.e. their semantic meaning is not expressed by their individual terms. To tackle this problem semantic theme classifications were proposed. One of the most prominent schemes was proposed by Kuusi (1972) and further widely adopted and explored in the literature (Lauhakangas, 2001; Lauhakangas, 2007). Kuusi developed a thematic classification of proverbs which consists of 13 main semantic themes and their 52 main classes divided into 325 subgroups. However, the structure of the thematic hierarchy is based on free associations that might in some cases be quite controversial. In addition, some of the theme classes represent the explicit terminology of the proverbs related to them (e.g. "natural elements"), while the others convey their implicit meaning (e.g. "social position"). Furthermore, every proverb belongs only to a single theme even when it clearly fits several themes, some by terms and the others by meaning.

These inconsistencies can be resolved by designing a multi-dimensional ontology with well-defined classes and properties (relationships), and which separates explicit terminology classes from the semantic meaning classes. Recently, multi-dimensional or multi-perspective ontologies have been proposed by information and computer scientists (e.g. Zhitomirsky-Geffet, Bar-Ilan, Miller, & Shoham, 2010). A multi-perspective ontology contains several categorization schemes, i.e. it is composed of multiple orthogonal sets of categories. Each of these sets describes a different aspect or dimension of the classified objects.

The goal of this research is to develop a generic ontological model for proverbs that unifies potential classification criteria and various characteristics of proverbs at different dimensions. Since proverbs, as mentioned above, can be described and indexed by multiple characteristics and criteria, we suggest that multi-dimensional ontologies fit very well for proverb classification.

To test the proposed methodology and the effectiveness of the constructed ontological model we developed an online proverb search and retrieval system. Using this system we conducted a large-scale user experiment. In our experiment 70 users were divided into two groups and asked to search a proverb repository using two different interfaces: free-text search interface and ontology-based interface. The first group was first exposed to the ontology search and then to the free-text search interface, while the second group first used the free-text search interface and then the ontology-based search. At the end of the experiment, the users were asked to evaluate their search experience with both interfaces in a short questionnaire. The results of the experiment were analyzed by standard recall and precision measures and the questionnaire was analyzed by standard statistical methods.

The following research questions were investigated in the user study:

- 1) Whether and how much is ontology-based search more effective than the free-text search for proverb retrieval in terms of precision and recall?
- 2) Whether the ontology helps minimize user effort during proverb search compared to the free-text search?
- 3) What is the level of user satisfaction with the ontology-based search system compared to the free-text search?
- 4) Whether the order of exposure to the interfaces (ontology-based search first or free-text search first) influences the results?
- 5) What is the most popular search strategy applied by users to retrieve proverbs when using ontology vs. without ontology?
- 6) Whether proverbs with high user consensus ("wisdom of the crowds") yield higher recall and precision than all the user selected proverbs (evaluated by experts' selected golden standard)?

The introduced classification model provides researchers, publicists and writers, literature and linguistics teachers and students and all the folklore lovers with the semantic ontology-based search of proverbs by various aspects and criteria, including explicit terminology and semantic meaning. A practical contribution of this work is an automated web-based proverb search and retrieval system which incorporates the proposed multi-dimensional ontological scheme.

Related work

To the best of our knowledge, there are no existing ontologies for proverbs. Therefore, in this section we review related work in the field of cultural heritage ontologies. Many of them are also multi-dimensional ontologies, which are particularly relevant for our study.

Two fundamental upper-level ontologies were recently developed for the domain of cultural heritage by two large research groups: CIDOC-CRM, a result of a 10-year project (<http://www.cidoc-crm.org/>, Doerr, 2003) and Europeana Data Model (Winer, 2011, 2014).

They are being successfully employed and extended by many national projects for cultural heritage digitization. One example is a metrical ontology for Spanish poetry (González-Blanco et al., 2014). This ontological model includes all the common structural characteristics of ancient poetry from different time periods and genres and thus provides a common

terminology for linking various repertoires. The ontology was constructed in two steps: 1) the generic ontology for the shared genre-independent characteristics of the poems; and then 2) enrichment of the ontology with specific concepts and properties specific for Castilian poetry. Another extension of the CIDOC-CRM model and FRBRoo ontology (Bekiari, Doerr, & Le Boeuf, 2010) for bibliographic data is the SAWS ontology built as part of the Sharing Ancient Wisdoms project. This project focuses on collections of ideas and opinions which make up the ancient genre of philosophical texts, Wisdom Literature. An ontology for describing the types of relationships present between or within these texts has been constructed (<http://www.ancientwisdoms.ac.uk>; http://www.ancientwisdoms.ac.uk/media/ontology/doc – SAWS_ontology). SAWS concentrates mainly on Ancient Greek and Arabic manuscripts containing wisdom literature. All class descriptions were provided by domain experts.

In (Luchev, Paneva & Rangochev, 2008) the authors introduce a generic ontological model of knowledge of art objects that belong to Bulgarian folklore. This model is a step towards building a digital library of Bulgarian folklore tradition and contains 70 concepts (such as "Song", "Ritual", "Faith" and "Food") and 81 properties.

Recently, an ontology for Chinese poetry has been developed by combining the well-known Chinese vocabulary thesaurus (TYCCL) with poems and resources (Yang, Tseng, Liao, & Liang, 2013). First, a set of keywords has been selected as representative of 300 Chinese poems by consulting a domain expert. Some of the keywords conveyed some information on a poem such as, "poem title", "person's name", "building name", and "location name", while the other keywords were abstract e.g. "love", "farewell", or "sad". This ontology allowed rapid access to poems that contain user query terms.

Another related project is a collaborative generation of a multi-perspective ontology from users tags for images of Jewish cultural heritage (Zhitomirsky-Geffet et al., 2010). As an image might be perceived differently by users with varying interests and viewpoints (e.g., historical object vs. religious symbol), a mechanism for expressing various user perspectives has been integrated into the ontology. Each perspective including its concepts and their interrelationships can be viewed as a separate dimension of the ontology.

In this study we adopted and combined the methodological approaches presented in the reviewed literature above. Thus, we use and inherit entities from the existing generic models, build the ontological model with multiple dimensions, perform two-phase design that consists of the upper-level ontology and its extension, use a corpus of representative objects (proverbs) to fetch the basic vocabulary and employ the ontology to improve search and retrieval. Our methodology is described in greater detail in the next section.

Research Methodology

At the first stage of the research we developed a methodology for creating a multi-dimensional ontological model for proverbs. Then, this methodology was applied on a set of proverbs, an ontology was constructed, and further utilized as part of the proverb retrieval system. Finally, a large-scale user study was arranged to evaluate the effectiveness of the created ontology.

The process of ontology creation consists of two steps: 1) creating the generic upper-ontology for proverbs based on the existing models; and 2) then refining and extending it with more specific classes and relationships from a selected proverb corpus. The upper-level ontology for proverbs is generic and can be easily translated into different languages. It will serve for interoperability purposes. The lower level ontology is facilitated to represent the realm of Hebrew proverbs.

The upper-ontology creation for proverbs

To build an upper ontological model for proverbs we explored the existing ontologies in the field of cultural heritage, such as CIDOC-CRM (<http://www.cidoc-crm.org/>, Doerr, 2003), FRBR-OO (Bekiari et. al. 2010), SAWS (<http://www.ancientwisdoms.ac.uk/>), and DM2E (<http://dm2e.eu>). The classes most related to proverbs include:

- 1) E33_Linguistic_object in CIDOC_CRM – *"This class comprises identifiable expressions in natural language. Instances of E33_Linguistic_Object can be expressed in many ways: e.g. as written texts, recorded speech or sign language. However, the CRM treats instances of E33 Linguistic Object independently from the medium or method by which they are expressed."*
- 2) F2:Expression in FRBR-OO – *"This class comprises the intellectual or artistic realisations of works in the form of identifiable immaterial objects, such as texts, poems, jokes, musical or choreographic notations, movement pattern, sound pattern, images, multimedia objects, or any combination of such forms that have objectively recognisable structures."*
- 3) edm:ProvidedCHO (Provided Cultural Heritage Object) class in DM2E – *"This class comprises the Cultural Heritage objects that Europeana collects descriptions about."*

We defined a new class Proverb as a subclass of the three classes above as follows, where rdf and rdfs are RDF/S language namespaces, ecrm is the namespace of CRM-CIDOC, efrbroo stands for the namespace of FRBR-OO and edm is the DM2E model namespace:

```
<rdfs:Class rdf:ID="Proverb">
  <rdfs:SubClassOf rdf:resource="#ecrm:E33_Linguistic_Object"/>
  <rdfs:SubClassOf rdf:resource="#edm:ProvidedCHO"/>
  <rdfs:SubClassOf rdf:resource="#efrbroo:F23_Expression"/>
</rdfs:Class>
```

This class inherits the above properties from its super-classes. In particular, the *dc:description* property contains the text of the proverb, and other *metadata* properties such as, *edm:genre* states whether the proverb is literal or idiomatic, *efrbroo:has component* property holds the main terms of the proverb that are to be searchable, *ecrm:has language* comprises the language of the proverb and *ecrm:has translation* is used for the proverb's translation.

Next, the proverb *content* is to be considered. One of the main characteristics of proverbs content is that their meaning is typically metaphoric and is not expressed explicitly by their terminology. Hence, there is a need in modeling proverbs' content at two distinct but inter-related dimensions: 1) the explicit terminology (ET); and 2) the metaphoric terminology (MT). Each of these dimensions consists of a set of classes and triples, which correspond to literal or semantic (metaphoric) subjects of proverbs. To create the upper-ontology for

proverb subjects we set the root (most abstract) class of the entire hierarchy to be "Entity" and define its two direct subclasses as Explicit subject and Metaphoric subject classes. For the upper-level ontology at the ET dimension we chose the following generic classes based on the WordNet ontology (Fellbaum, 1998): physical entity, abstract entity and living entity. At the MT dimension we selected the following most generic Kuusi's categories: social element, cognitive element, element in human life, element of time, element of religion.

The Conceptual Mapping (CM) Model (Ahrens, 2002) and the Contemporary Theory of Metaphor (Lakoff, 1993) analyze the linguistic correspondences between a source and a target (knowledge) domain in order to determine the underlying reason for the source-target pairings. The underlying reason is formulated in terms of a Mapping Principle, that a target domain will select only source domains that involve unique mapping principles. Inspired by this theory, matching pairs of subjects (*source* – from the ET dimension and *target* from the MT dimension) associated with the same proverb, will be linked by a new ontological property: *has metaphoric target*. Table 1 demonstrates a sample proverbs and their semantic interpretation.

In addition, we define the following new properties of the Proverb class: *has interpretation* (semantic meaning) of the proverb (string), *has explicit subject* and *has metaphoric subject*. The values for both types of subjects are of E55_Type from the CRM-CIDOC model and are defined in the bi-dimensional ontology of proverbs' subjects described above. *ecrm:E55_Type* class's *has broader term* and *has narrower term* properties are employed in defining the taxonomy of subjects for both subject ontology dimensions, ET and MT. Additional properties represent other dimensions of proverbs such as, *has syntactic structure* and *has logical structure* (Hasan-Rotem & Katz, 2009). However, in this study we focus on the ET and MT dimensions of proverbs and leave the other dimensions for future research.

An instance sample of the Proverb Class (for proverb no. 3 in Table 1) is shown in Figure 1.

```

<prv:Proverb rdf:ID="P1">
<dc:description> בור ששתית ממנו מים אל תזרוק בו אבן. </dc:description >
<ecrm:haslanguage> Hebrew </ecrm:haslanguage>
<ecrm:hastranslation> Cast no stone into the well that gives you water.
</ecrm:hastranslation>
<edm:genre> Idiom </edm:genre>
<prv:hasinterpretation> Don't be ungrateful and reward evil to a person who did you
good. </prv: hasinterpretation >
<prv:hasexplicitsubject rdf:resource="#Stone"/>
<prv:hasmetaphoricsubject rdf:resource="#Ungratefulness"/>
<prv:hasexplicitsubject rdf:resource="#Water"/>
<prv:hasmetaphoricsubject rdf:resource="#Kindness"/>
<prv:hasexplicitsubject rdf:resource="#Well"/>
<prv:hasmetaphoricsubject rdf:resource="#Person"/>
</prv:Proverb>

```

Figure :1 A sample instance of the proverb class with the various properties.

Proverb text	Proverb interpretation	Metaphor source-target pairs
(3) Cast no stone into the well that gives you water .	Don't be ungrateful and reward evil to a person who did you good .	Stone – reward evil, ungratefulness Water – good, kindness Well - person
(35) Cast your bread upon the waters , for you will find it after many days.	Do good unto your fellow man , even if you do not immediately benefit from it, for in the long run you will be rewarded .	Bread – good Water – man Find (bread) – be rewarded
(42) Go to the ant , O sluggard ; consider her ways and be wise .	This proverb praises the ant's diligence and offers it as an example to learn from. A lazy person should learn diligence from the ant which is fabled for its diligence.	Ant – diligence Sluggard – lazy person Wise - diligent

Table1: A sample of proverbs with their semantic interpretation and source-target pairs of terms from ET and MT dimensions. The key terms in both proverbs and their interpretations are marked by bold font.

Figure 2: This figure demonstrates a fragment of the proverb ontology linked with the two-dimensional ontology translated into English. The concepts of the metaphoric dimension are purple, while the concepts of the explicit terminology dimension are pink. "Human trait" and its hyponyms belong to both dimensions, therefore they are split and are colored with both colors simultaneously.

—> The single-solid arrows represent the taxonomic relationships (sometimes indirect, e.g. between "ant" and "living entity" there is a more general concept, "animal", that was omitted for simplicity of the diagram).

==> The blue double-solid arrows stand for the *instance-of* relationships.

==> The purple double-solid arrows show the *has subject* relationships.

==> The double-slashed arrows between proverbs and concepts represent the *has metaphoric subject* relationships.

==> The double-slashed arrows between two concepts correspond to the *has metaphoric target* relationships.

Extending the proverb subjects' ontology with concepts from the proverb corpus

Once the upper-ontology has been constructed, it can be enriched with more specific classes associated with specific proverbs collection. We propose a general methodology for this process. First, the raw vocabulary (ET) of the proverbs is to be normalized, extended and

formulated, in order to build the bi-dimensional ontology. To this end, we took a bottom-up approach divided into the following steps:

1. At first, all the individual terms with self-defined meaning are extracted, nouns (transformed into their basic morphologic derivation and singular form), verbs and adjectives (transformed into their noun form), and multi-term collocations are retrieved as well in their singular form (e.g. "good fortune", "spilt milk").
2. Synonyms and similar terms are unified into WordNet-style. Each synset represents a concept in the ontology.
3. Pairs of the created concepts (synsets) are inter-linked by hyponymy relationship and additional abstract concepts from WordNet are added as hypernyms at the upper level of the hierarchy. In addition a few concepts of parallel themes from the Kuusi's scheme (<http://lauhakan.home.cern.ch/lauhakan/etsi.asp>) are incorporated as well, such as "natural element" and "animal".
4. The non-hierarchical and domain specific relationship types between the concepts are added. Thus, the creation of the ET (explicit terminology) dimension of the ontology is finalized.
5. The next phase is to construct the MT (metaphoric terminology) dimension of the ontology. Most of the proverb terms include metaphors which refer to a different meaning in another semantic field. Therefore, we further detect all the concepts that are used as metaphors in the corresponding proverbs to compose a set of their semantic interpretation concepts (e.g. for the concept "lion", a concept "leader" was added into the MT concept set). The interpretation terms are mostly extracted from the proverb meaning description appearing on the above websites.
6. Further, steps 2-4 above are to be repeated for the MT concept set.
7. Finally, to bind the metaphoric concepts to their semantic interpretations, a new cross-dimensional relationship type "has metaphoric target" is employed.
8. Once the ontological structure is complete, each concept from both dimensions is linked to its proverbs.

The ontology-based system for proverb search

Finally, to facilitate the proposed ontological model for real life applications, a web-based proverb retrieval system was implemented by adapting the interfaces from the previous work (Bar-Ilan, Zhitomirsky-Geffet, Miller, & Shoham, 2012) and can be accessed on <http://www.ontology.org.il/>. Two interfaces were constructed to enable object (in our case proverb) retrieval from the database based on query terms selected by users: 1) ontology-based interface, and 2) free-text search interface. In the ontology-based interface the query terms could be selected from the ontology while in the free-text search interface there was no ontology available, but rather a plain textbox with autocomplete from the flat list of terms coming from the proverbs or their interpretations. To start working with the system a user had to login into one of the two interfaces (a different user name was provided for each interface) and then choose a scenario from the scenario list. Then, the user had to pick term/s and construct the query for search. In each of the interfaces clicking on the search button retrieved the list of proverbs that were linked with the selected concepts (with the exception of expanded search, where additional related proverbs were retrieved as well). Figure 3 displays part of the results for the query "Success". The users were asked to mark all the

Figure 3: The system interface for proverb search and retrieval with the two-dimensional ontology.

proverbs that were relevant to the specific scenario along with their semantic interpretations. The users also had an option to see all the proverbs they picked as relevant for each of the scenarios, and they could remove proverbs from this set if they felt that they were not really relevant for the scenario. Then, another scenario could be selected for search by the user.

The main ontology-based search interface of the system is displayed in Figure 3. Note that query terms for proverb search might be first looked up in the ontology. This can be done by picking a dimension (explicit or metaphoric) and then browsing the taxonomy of this dimension or by searching the ontology by typing a term in the textbox. When a specific concept was found and selected in the ontology, all the related concepts from both dimensions are displayed and can be added to the query either manually or by activating the automatic "query expansion" option. The semantic links (by "has metaphoric target" relationship) between the concepts from different dimensions enable sophisticated cross-dimensional queries, such as: "find proverbs on people's social positions". The retrieved proverbs might not include the original query terms at all, but only their related concepts in the ontology (e.g. "leader", "lion"). To the best of our knowledge this is the first system for proverb retrieval by semantic meaning.

Figure 4: Free-text search interface with autocomplete.

The ontology was displayed in four columns (see Figure 3). The rightmost column listed the dimensions (Hebrew is written from right to left). Selecting a dimension displayed all the concepts assigned to the dimension in the third column from right. In the second and the fourth column related concepts are shown. In the second column from the right only hierarchically related concepts are shown, while in the fourth column from the right hierarchically related child concepts as well as otherwise related concepts (e.g. *part-of*, *time*, *location*, *agent*) are shown. A mouse over these concepts shows the exact relation between the selected concept in the third column and the concept in the fourth column. Double clicking on a concept selects it as a search term. Several concepts could be selected (interpreted as a Boolean AND) (Bar-Ilan et al., 2010, page 3).

As a baseline for comparative evaluation, an alternative interface was implemented, a free-text search Google style (see Figure 4) interface with auto-completion from terms of all the proverbs and also from proverbs' semantic interpretations available online (recall that the terms of the ontology were also taken mostly from the proverbs and their interpretations). This interface enabled searching for proverbs linked with two or more terms (Boolean AND). In order to search for concepts that contained more than one word the users had to use quotation marks (Bar-Ilan et al., 2010, page 3).

Experimental setup

First, we applied the proposed methodology on the domain of Hebrew proverbs and two basic dimensions of proverbs were composed: (1) the explicit terminology (ET); and (2) the metaphoric terminology (MT). To this end, as a case study a set of one hundred popular Hebrew proverbs was created. A proverb was selected to be one of the one hundred only if its

popularity in use by native speakers is high (as assessed by the third author of the paper), and if it appeared and its source was cross verified in all three reliable online Hebrew proverb collections:

- The virtual library site of the Israeli Ministry of Education (<http://lib.cet.ac.il/>)
- Wiktionary(<http://he.wiktionary.org/wiki/>)
- Wikiquote (<http://en.wikiquote.org/wiki/Category:Proverbs>).

An additional criterion for proverb selection was to ensure they cover a broad spectrum of topics and as many Kuusi categories (<http://lauhakan.home.cern.ch/lauhakan/etsi.asp>) as possible.

Overall, our ontology for a hundred proverbs consisted of 405 concepts (synsets) and related concept triples (677) on the ET dimension, and 120 concepts and 166 triples on the MT dimension. Mostly the concept sets of the two dimensions were disjoint having only 12% (63) concepts in common (such as, "Human traits" in Figure 2). For some proverbs these concepts appear in the text and thus are included in the ET dimension, but for others they belong to the semantic meaning of the proverb, and therefore, are part of the MT dimension taxonomy. The major classes of the ET dimension were "physical entity" (46 associated proverbs) and "living entity" (46 associated proverbs) and the MT concepts mostly concentrate in the field of "social element" (50 proverbs), "element of human life" (18 proverbs), cognition (17 proverbs) and "morality" (16 proverbs). Two additional popular categories were "Person" (47 proverbs) and "human trait" (51 proverbs) that were common for both dimensions. The upper-level ontology and the proverbs were further translated into English and also to the formal RDF/S representation. To this end, English proverbs closest in meaning to the original Hebrew proverbs were located. Both Hebrew and English versions are available at <http://www.ontology.org.il>.

To evaluate the effectiveness of the ontology for proverb retrieval compared to the free-text search approach a user study was arranged with methodology adopted from (Bar-Ilan et al., 2012). To this end, 70 participants (students in the Information Science department), in two randomly assigned groups of about 35 participants each, were asked to select all the proverbs that they found relevant to each of the ten scenarios (tasks) presented to them. The average age of the participants was 26 and 85% of them were under the age of 30.

The scenarios were the following:

1. Human wisdom: Find all the proverbs in which "wisdom" is expressed through the senses and body limbs.
2. Failure and success: Find all proverbs which deal with failure and success.
3. Quantitative advantage: Find all proverbs which deal with quantitative advantage as a factor which leads to success and qualitative advantage as well as those that show the opposite, i.e. a numerical advantage does not lead to success at all.
4. Water: Find all the proverbs where the word "water" appears in the sense of well, help, caring and kindness.

Figure 5: The number of the relevant proverbs for experts' vs. user consensus assessment.

5. Wealth: Find all the proverbs relating directly or indirectly to social classes, especially to wealth and to wealthy people.

6. Deception: Find all the proverbs relating to the issue of deception, for example, when external traits are not identical to internal traits and in which a certain idea and its opposite appear in the same proverb.

7. Human traits: Find all the proverbs in which various human characteristics are compared to animals.

8. Leaders: Find all the proverbs that show the positive and negative sides of leaders, rulers and influential people.

9. Reward: Find all proverbs which deal with the ideas of "reward", in the positive and negative senses, "judgment", "reward and punishment" and the compensation a person will receive for his actions.

10. Work: Find all the proverbs that emphasize the importance of work and diligence as well as those that deal with futile effort.

Note that scenarios 1 ("human wisdom"), 7 ("human traits") and 4 ("water") are explicitly cross-dimensional and require results that are in the intersection of both dimensions of the ontology. For example, for scenario no.1, relevant proverbs include terms related to senses and body limbs (e.g. "eye", "head", "hearing") from the ET dimension of the ontology, whose metaphoric targets are related to wisdom in the MT dimension. We anticipate that the proposed ontology with the *has metaphoric target* property could be especially effective for this kind of scenarios.

The proverbs, tasks and the terminology were all in Hebrew. Each group had two search sessions: each with a different subset of the above scenarios and with a different interface.

G1/G4 – These participants first searched the database through a free-text search for the first five scenarios above (we denote this searching session as G1) and then they switched the interface to the ontology-based interface and worked with the other five scenarios in the list (referred as G4 throughout this article).

G2/G3 – The participants in this group did their first search session with the ontology-based interface and the first five scenarios (G2 session) above and then moved to the textbox search with the last five scenarios (G3 session).

Prior to the experiment, the participants were instructed by the authors on how to use each of the interfaces by demonstrating the search with the system for two “training” scenarios (proverbs on family relationships and proverbs on timing and its importance). Then the participants were given an opportunity to practice using each of the interfaces (before starting the main experiment) to search for proverbs on the value of silence. The participants were also provided with a document describing all the existing search options in both interfaces. Two of the authors were present the whole time of the experiment in order to supply technical support to the participants who needed more help while working with the system.

The participants were asked to locate as many proverbs for a project on a given scenario as they could. They were particularly guided to pick as relevant proverbs that reflect all the aspects of the scenario. In addition, we were interested in users’ satisfaction with the system and with the search interfaces. After finishing both search sessions, the participants answered a short questionnaire. It included Likert scale and assertion questions on whether the database contained relevant proverbs for the scenarios, on their satisfaction with each of the search interface and on the quality of the concepts in the ontology. They were also asked about their level of familiarity with the proverbs. In addition there were two open questions, one on the retrieval method they employed and another where they were asked to express their positive and negative impressions of the system. The entire experiment including both search sessions and filling up the questionnaire was limited to approximately ninety minutes and all the participants have managed to complete it in time.

The golden standard relevance of the proverbs for the scenarios was assessed by the authors in two stages. First, for each scenario, each of the three authors individually and systematically examined each of the 100 proverbs in the database and decided whether it was relevant for the specific scenario or not. The relevance criteria for proverbs were similar to the user guidelines above: 1) a proverb could be used for a project that would be prepared on a given scenario, and 2) the proverb reflects all the aspects of the scenario. After the individual relevance assessments stage, the authors discussed their choices on the set of relevant proverbs for each scenario, and reached an agreement in cases of contradictory individual judgments. . Note that each of the authors is at least 40 years old (substantially older than the participants of the experiment), has a wide writing experience in Hebrew, and possesses at least an M.A. degree (two of the authors have an academic degree on Hebrew linguistics and/or literature). Relevance based on the judgment of the authors is called *expert relevance* and is denoted *Rel_exp*. On average, 6.7 relevant proverbs were determined for each scenario.

The results were also assessed by pooling the proverbs retrieved by the users for each scenario. Only proverbs retrieved by at least ten users for the given scenario and search interface were considered. As a result, two lists of proverbs relevant for at least 10 users were

created for each of the interfaces and merged together. This is an additional relevance golden standard, called *user consensus relevance* in the paper, and is denoted *Rel_user*. On average, 6.3 relevant proverbs were selected for each scenario by user consensus.

Results and discussion

User consensus versus expert relevance assessments

The number of relevant proverbs selected by experts was higher than the user consensus proverbs for 7 out of 10 scenarios (see Figure 5). As expected for free-text search the number of consensus proverbs selected by the users was lower than the number of proverbs selected by the experts and they were all included in the experts' list of relevant proverbs for 8 out of 10 scenarios. This is because the experts examined each proverb and the users retrieved proverbs using a search interface. This is in contrast to the findings of (Bar-Ilan et al., 2010) for image retrieval where there were more user consensus images than experts' relevant images. The reason for this could be that proverbs are very hard to retrieve by standard search compared to regular text documents and even to tagged images.

For the ontology-based search for 6 out of 10 scenarios all the consensus relevant proverbs were included in the list of experts' relevant proverbs. For this interface, for 4 out of 10 scenarios there were 1-2 more proverbs tagged as relevant by the user consensus not included in the experts' relevant proverbs. The reason for this disagreement was that users considered proverbs with a more general interpretation than defined in the scenarios as relevant (e.g. a term "water" occurs in the proverb, but not in the meaning of kindness, instead of "wisdom" the proverbs are about unwise or about good people, instead of "wealthy people" the proverb refers to money in general).

Interestingly, 96% of the free-text search consensus relevance proverbs were included in the ontology-based consensus relevance proverb list meaning that the inter-user agreement for consensus proverbs is very high. The recall and precision of user consensus vs. experts is shown in Table 4. The relatively high scores for both recall and precision (over 80%) for the ontology-based interface indicate that our scenarios were clearly defined.

Scenarios	Free-text precision	Free-text recall	Ontology-based precision	Ontology-based recall	The proportion of the free-text consensus proverbs included in the ontology-based consensus proverbs
Human wisdom	1	0.50	0.67	1	1
Failure and success	1	0.29	0.91	0.71	1
Quantitative advantage	1	0.40	0.60	0.60	1
Water	0.50	0.50	0.80	1	1
Wealth	0.75	0.43	1	1	1

Deception	1	0.40	1	0.80	1
Human trait	1	0.33	1	0.67	1
Work	1	0.43	1	0.71	0.67
Leaders	1	0.33	1	0.83	1
Reward	0.67	0.33	1	0.83	1
Average	0.89	0.39	0.90	0.82	0.97
Stdev	0.18	0.07	0.15	0.15	0.11

Table 2: Recall and precision of the user consensus relevance evaluated by expert relevance for different interfaces and scenarios.

Precision				
	Rel_expert		Rel_user	
Scenario	Ontology-based G2/G4	Free-text G1/G3	Ontology-based G2/G4	Free-text G1/G3
Human wisdom	0.49	0.43	0.64	0.56
Failure and success	0.74	0.87	0.70	0.85
Quantitative advantage	0.36	0.62	0.52	0.51
Water	0.66	0.52	0.91	0.87
Wealth	0.87	0.83	0.90	0.98
Deception	0.71	0.51	0.62	0.49
Human trait	0.69	0.62	0.59	0.54
Leaders	0.89	0.68	0.85	0.67
Reward	0.74	0.51	0.69	0.63
Work	0.70	0.70	0.68	0.70
Average	0.69	0.63	0.71	0.68
Stdev	0.16	0.14	0.13	0.17

Table 3: Average precision for every scenario and interface for user consensus vs. expert evaluation.

Recall				
	Rel_expert		Rel_user	
Scenario	Ontology-based	Free-text G1/G3	Ontology-based G2/G4	Free-text G1/G3

	G2/G4			
Human wisdom	0.68	0.34	0.59	0.29
Failure and success	0.41	0.24	0.51	0.32
Quantitative advantage	0.40	0.25	0.54	0.22
Water	0.70	0.35	0.63	0.46
Wealth	0.65	0.34	0.59	0.38
Deception	0.60	0.31	0.66	0.37
Human trait	0.44	0.27	0.56	0.33
Leaders	0.66	0.33	0.75	0.38
Reward	0.69	0.38	0.62	0.47
Work	0.56	0.34	0.62	0.40
Average	0.58	0.32	0.61	0.36
Stdev	0.12	0.05	0.07	0.08

Table 4: Average recall for every scenario and interface for user consensus vs. expert evaluation.

Next, we compute precision and recall for all the proverbs retrieved by the participants according to both kinds of relevance assessment, user consensus relevance and expert relevance.

Recall and precision

The average number of proverbs retrieved by the participants for the free-text search was 3.72 while the average number of proverbs retrieved by the participants for the ontology-based search was 5.11 (recall that the average number of relevant proverbs according to the experts was 6.7). Hence, the ontology helped retrieve more proverbs. However, not all of them were relevant. Thus, the average precision values for the different scenarios and user groups are displayed in Table 4. Recall that groups G1 and G4 used search box interfaces, while G2 and G3 worked with the ontology interface. Precision per scenario and group was calculated using both golden standards. As can be observed from Table 4 all the average precision scores were quite close but a bit higher (up to 10%) for the ontology-based search interface and the standard deviations are quite low. In 7 out of 10 scenarios this interface yielded higher precision. But for some scenarios like "failure and success" the free-text search produced better precision, but much lower recall as can be viewed in Table 5. Although the average precision using user consensus relevance is a bit higher than based on expert relevance assessments, but for half of the scenarios the expert relevance evaluation produced higher precision. Also standard deviation values are very high. These findings indicate that there is no clearly "best" evaluation type and interface in terms of precision.

Average recall values per scenario and group based on expert and user relevance judgments are displayed in Table 5. In this case, as well, user consensus evaluation is a bit higher than the expert-based one. However, there is a clear significant advantage (of 70-80% on average) of ontology-based interface over the free-text search interface in terms of recall for all the scenarios. The highest recall for ontology-based search (but not for free-text search) was achieved for the cross-dimensional "human wisdom" and "water", which indicates the effectiveness of the ontology for such complicated cases. Especially hard scenarios were "failure and success", "human trait" and "quantitative advantage". The reason could be a relatively high number of relevant proverbs and the less clear, more abstract meaning of the latter scenario. It should be noted that the user consensus ("wisdom of the crowds") recall and precision evaluated by experts' relevance (see Table 3) for both interfaces are much higher (by 25-40%) than the individual users recall and precision values (displayed in Tables 4, 5).

We also investigated the influence of the order of exposure to the interfaces on the obtained results. In G2 the ontology was used first and for G1 the free-text search was used first. In both sessions the first five scenarios from section 3 were searched. The average precision of G2 was 0.62, which was by 14% lower than the average precision of G1 (0.66). The average recall of G2 was 0.57, which was by 90% higher than G1's recall (0.30). On the other hand, in G4 the ontology was used after the free-text search session and also for G3 the free-text search was employed after the ontology-based search session. The average recall of G4 is 0.59 which is by 79% higher than the average recall of G3 (0.33), while the average precision of G4 is (0.75) which is much higher (by 25%) than of G3 (0.60). These figures reflect the possible influence of the order of exposure to the interfaces on the search precision: once

Figure 6: The average number of searches for ontology-based and free-text interfaces for different scenarios. All the differences between the ontology-based and free-text search interfaces are significant with t-test at $p < .01$.

having some experience with the free-text search, it is possible to achieve higher precision with the ontology-based search.

Search efficiency and user effort

The number of searches for every scenario and interface (see Figure 6) shows that ontology also helped minimize the user effort and search efficiency, as the subjects could locate the most relevant query terms more easily through the ontology and/or use the expanded search option instead of searching for many specific terms that they could come up with or by employing autocomplete. The differences between the scenarios are very pronounced especially for the free-text search (standard deviation is 5.13). This could be possibly explained by the relative difficulty of some scenarios over the others, such as "deception", for which there were only a few relevant proverbs in the database. Also, for the last five scenarios much more free-text searches (group G3) were conducted than for the first five scenarios (G1), while for the first five scenarios more ontology-based searches were conducted (G2) than for the last five scenarios (G4). In both cases, more searches were conducted when the subjects had already some experience with the system (although with a different interface). Thus, we conclude that the order of the exposure to the interfaces influences the number of performed searches.

User satisfaction

In the previous subsections we saw that in terms of precision the text box based and ontology-based interfaces performed quite similarly. In terms of recall the ontology interface was the best. Next, we analyzed and compared the user satisfaction with each of the interfaces.

As part of the questionnaire the subjects had to assess the effectiveness and easiness of use for each of the interfaces. The average satisfaction rate with the effectiveness of the ontology-based interface was significantly higher than of the free-text search interface (3.48 vs. 2.95, respectively). In particular, 62% of the subjects assessed the ontology-based interface as 4 or 5 (in the 1-5 Likert scale with 1 being the most negative answer), while only 31% of the subjects assessed the free-text search with these high effectiveness rates. Similarly, the majority of the subjects (63%) assessed the ontology-based interface as easy and fast to use (rates 4 and 5 out of 5) vs. only 33% who assigned high rates to free-text search interface for this question. The above differences were found significant by t-test with $p < .01$.

Therefore, we conclude that in terms of user satisfaction with the interface, the users preferred the ontology-based search rather than free-text type interface. This is in contrast with previous research in (Bar-Ilan et al., 2012) and (Hearst & Rosner, 2008). A reason for this is that in the case of proverbs the usage of terms is mostly metaphoric and the themes of the proverbs are worded differently from their literal terminology. Hence, it was very difficult to locate proverbs by the scenario terms without the ontology that shows all the related concepts for the term searched by the user. Thus, the most popular search strategy for the free-text search reported by 40% of the participants was: "to think of the proverbs relevant for a scenario and search by their key terms." Many of these subjects also searched for synonyms of the relevant proverbs' terms and their semantic interpretation.

On the other hand, using the ontology the most popular strategy (reported by over 25% of the subjects) was to search in the ontology for terms from the scenario definition and semantic interpretation of proverbs and then locate more relevant terms through ontological relationships: "In the ontology-based interface I did not have to think of proverbs so much as ontology helped with this"; and "locating the proverbs with the ontology was easier and more effective than through free-text search, since there was no need to think of very specific terms that appear in the relevant proverbs, but to search for more general themes/topics while more specific terms are related to them in the ontology and thus can be easily located." For example, for scenario no. 1, "human wisdom expressed through the senses and body limbs", the most popular terms in the ontology-based search were "body limb", "sense" and "wisdom", while for free-text search a list of various body limbs, such as "eye", "head", "ear" and senses like "hearing", "vision" were used. Also about 35% answered that they used "expanded search" to find more relevant search terms. Thus, we conclude that participants preferred the ontological search due to its ability to provide semantically related terms (from both explicit and metaphoric dimensions) to those initially chosen by the user. This could be particularly achieved by using the ontology search and further browsing features and through the automatic query expansion feature. The related terms from the ontology reminded users of more relevant terms, contexts and specific proverbs and consequently, directly lead to more relevant proverbs in the final search results for a scenario.

In addition, the participants were asked to assess the amount of relevant terms in the ontology and in the autocomplete mechanism of the free-text search interface. The majority of the

participants for both interfaces (58% for the ontology and 65% for the free-text autocomplete) reported that there were enough terms to retrieve relevant proverbs". Interestingly, despite the higher user satisfaction with the number of terms for free-text search, the effectiveness and recall of the retrieved proverbs was much lower for this interface.

We also found that about 11% of the subjects were not familiar with most of the proverbs (according to their own self-assessment in the questionnaire). Only one of them was a new immigrant and all of them were younger than 25. This finding sheds some light on the differences in language knowledge between generations.

Finally, in an open-ended question the study participants were requested to comment on the retrieval process in general. Most of the comments were in favor of the ontology-based search. For instance, "it is obvious that the ontology-based search is better than free-text search", "through ontology-based search I was able to locate many relevant proverbs, that I could not find with the free-text search"; "the ontological search helps since it retrieves results according to the term inter-relationships and not just by specific terms and the interface was very easy to use"; "this (through ontological search) is a very effective way to learn new proverbs, the retrieval is easy once you understand how the system works"; "the ontology helps remind you of the relevant proverbs you know"; "this kind of system with ontological search could be very useful for new immigrants and language learners who are not so familiar with Hebrew proverbs". Thus, the participants preferred the ontological interface since it enabled proverb retrieval by the given terms' relationships with other terms, i.e. search expanded by contexts, rather than by individual terms that a user could come up with.

There were also four negative comments about ontology: "the ontology-based search is not intuitive enough especially in the age of Google and you need to learn it first in order to use it successfully"; "I did not get along well with the ontology-based interface"; "the categories were not well organized" and "the ontology-based interface was complicated to use and not very user friendly".

Conclusions

In this study we proposed and formally defined a generic two-phase methodology for the creation of a multi-dimensional ontology for proverbs. The proposed methodology was further applied on a corpus of 100 popular Hebrew proverbs. To assess the quality of the created ontology, an ontology-based search interface was implemented. A user study with 70 participants demonstrated the advantages of ontology-based search over the free-text search utilized for proverbs. In particular, the results show an over 80% increase in recall and up to 10% in precision for ontology-based retrieval compared to the free-text search. Furthermore, the "wisdom of the crowds" relevance that includes only the proverbs retrieved by over 10 participants achieves results very close to the experts (90% precision and 82% recall) for the ontology-based interface.

In addition, we also found that the ontology substantially minimized the user effort in the search process. The ontology enabled the users to perform fewer searches for retrieving much more relevant proverbs. The analysis of the user satisfaction questionnaire was also more positive for the ontology-based search than for the free-text search (with the average scores of 3.48 vs. 2.95 out of 5, respectively). Thus, we conclude that in the case of proverbs, an

ontology is a necessary tool for effective and efficient search. This is in contrast with previous work (Bar-Ilan et al., 2012; Sinclair & Cardew-Hill, 2008)) with image and document retrieval where an ontology was found as the most effective in terms of recall only, but its effectiveness assessment for other parameters was controversial. Thus, in (Bar-Ilan et al., 2012) the authors report that for their image retrieval experiments with four different user interfaces, the term cloud and free-text search interfaces were more effective than ontology-based interface, in terms of precision (89.5%, 89.3% vs. 86.3%, correspondingly), while the ontology-based search achieved the best recall (37.8%) over the other interfaces (e.g. 35.3% for free-text search). For user satisfaction they found that the free-text search was assessed higher than the ontology-based interface (with the average scores of 4.26 vs. 3.76 out of 7, respectively). Sinclair & Cardew-Hill (2008) conducted an experiment comparing a folksonomy tag cloud and a free-text search interface for answering questions, on a set of textual documents. They found that when searching for specific information the free-text interface was preferred, while for more general tasks the folksonomy was preferred by the users. This difference between our results and the previous research can be explained by the fact that idiomatic and metaphoric expressions, which are frequent in proverbs, are very difficult to retrieve without the ontology that classifies the proverbs, links together their explicit and metaphoric terminology and enables search and browsing via related terms from different dimensions. In summary, the introduced ontological model provides researchers, publicists, language teachers and students and all folklore lovers with the semantic ontology-based search of proverbs by various aspects, including explicit terminology and semantic meaning.

The proposed ontological model can be easily extended with more dimensions. For example, a literary source taxonomy could be inserted into the model. Further work will enrich the resulting ontology with concepts created by collaborative tagging of new proverbs.

Acknowledgements

This research has been funded by the Barzilai Foundation. We are grateful to Pavel Kats for inspiration and fruitful discussions on the topic of proverb digitization.

References

- Ahrens, K. (2002). When love is not digested: Underlying reasons for source to target domain pairings in the contemporary theory of metaphor. In Y. E. Hsiao (ed.) *Proceedings of the First Cognitive Linguistics Conference*. (pp. 273-302). Taipei: Cheng-Chi University.
- Bar-Ilan, J., Zhitomirsky-Geffet M., Miller, Y. and S. Shoham. (2012). Tag-based Retrieval of Images through Different Interfaces - A User Study. *Online Information Review*, 36(5), 739 – 757.
- Bar-Ilan, J., Zhitomirsky-Geffet, M., Miller, Y. and Shoham, S. (2010). Tag cloud and ontology based retrieval of images. In *Proceedings of the Third Symposium of Information Interaction in Context (IiiX)*, 2010, New Brunswick, New Jersey, USA, pp. 85-94.
- Bekiari, C., Doerr, M., Le Boeuf P. (2010). FRBR object-oriented definition and mapping to FRBRER (version 1.0.1), International Working Group on FRBR and CIDOC

CRM Harmonisation supported by Delos NoE, January 2010. http://www.cidoc-crm.org/frbr_drafts.html

- Doerr, M. (2003). The CIDOC Conceptual Reference Module - an ontological approach to semantic interoperability of metadata. *AI Magazine*, 24(3), 75-92.
- Fellbaum, C. (Ed.). (1998). *WordNet: An electronic lexical database*. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press.
- González-Blanco, Elena, Seláf, Levente, Del Rio Riande, María Gimena, Martínez Cantón, Clara Isabel, Martos Pérez, & María Dolores. (June 2014) Building a metrical ontology as a model to link digital poetic repertoires. *Proceedings of the Digital humanities Conference Lausanne*. Retrieved September 05, 2014 from: <http://dharchive.org/paper/DH2014/Paper-674.xml>
- Gruber, T. R. (1995). Toward principles for the design of ontologies used for knowledge sharing?. *International journal of human-computer studies*, 43(5), 907-928.
- Hasan-Rokem, G., & Kats, P. (2009). From structural semantic analysis towards a computational proverbs classification framework. In K.J. Mckenna, (Ed), *The Proverbial "Pied Piper"* (pp. 111-125). New York: Peter Lang.
- Hearst, M. A., & Rosner, D. (2008, January). Tag clouds: Data analysis tool or social signaller?. In *Proceedings of the 41st Annual Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences*, (pp. 160-160). IEEE.
- Kuusi, M. (1972). Towards An International Type-System of Proverbs. *Proverbium* 19, 699-735.
- Lakoff, G. (1993). The Contemporary Theory of Metaphor. In A.Ortony (Ed.), *Metaphor and Thought* (2nd ed.). (pp. 202-251). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Lauhakangas, O. (2001). The Matti Kuusi International Type System of Proverbs. L. Honko, (Ed.): Helsinki, Suomalainen Tiedeakatemia Academia Scientiarum Fennica.
- Lauhakangas, O. (2007). Use of proverbs and narrative thought. *Folklore: Electronic Journal of Folklore*, (35), 77-84.
- Luchev, D., Paneva, D., & Rangochev, K. (2008). Use of Knowledge Technologies for Presentation of Bulgarian Folklore Heritage Semantics. *Information Technologies and Knowledge*, 2(4), 307-313.
- Noy, N.F. & McGuinness, D.L. (2001). *Ontology Development 101: A Guide to Creating Your First Ontology*. Technical Report KSL-01-05, Stanford Knowledge Systems Laboratory and Stanford Medical Informatics Technical Report SMI-2001-0880, Publisher: Citeseer, (pp. 1-25) doi: 10.1.1.136.5085
- Sinclair, J. and Cardew-Hall, M. (2008). The folksonomy cloud tag: When is it useful? *Journal of Information Science*, 34(1), 15-29.
- Winer, D. (2011). *Judaica Europeana D2.5: Semantic Interoperability Report with representation of selected controlled vocabularies in RDF/SKOS*. Semantic interoperability report with representation of selected controlled vocabularies in RDF/SKOS. Retrieved January 05, 2015 from: http://www.judaica-Europeana.eu/docs/D2-5_Semantic_interoperability_report.pdf

- Winer, D. (2014). Judaica Europeana: An Infrastructure for Aggregating Jewish Content. *Judaica Librarianship*, 18(1), 88–115. doi:10.14263/2330-2976.1027
- Yang, C. C., Tseng, S. S., Liao, A. Y., & Liang, T. (2013). Situated Poetry Learning Using Multimedia Resource Sharing Approach. *Educational Technology & Society*, 16(2), 282-295.
- Zhitomirsky-Geffet, M., Bar-Ilan, J., Miller, Y., & Shoham, S. (2010). A generic framework for collaborative multi-perspective ontology acquisition. *Online Information Review*, 34(1), 145-159.